

Synthesis of phenylthallium(III) dichloride and diphenylthallium(III) chloride complexes with bidentate Schiff base ligands : a photoelectron spectroscopic study

Shekhar Srivastava* and Abul Kalam

Department of Chemistry, Allahabad University, Allahabad-211 002, India

E-mail : shekharsril@rediffmail.com kalam_abul@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 20 February 2001, revised 5 September 2001, accepted 10 November 2001

Organothallium(III) derivatives of the formula R_nTlX_{3-n} and $R_nTlX_{3-n}D$ have been synthesized^{1,2}. Some of these derivatives have been reported to have industrial and biological uses¹. This paper reports phenylthallium(III) dichloride and diphenylthallium(III) chloride complexes with bidentate Schiff base ligands.

Results and Discussion

All the prepared molecular adducts were found to be stable in air. The observed molar conductance values of all the complexes in acetone ($20-30 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate that they are non-electrolyte³. All these prepared molecular adducts exhibited the $\nu_{C=N}$ band around $1620-1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which normally appeared at $1640-1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands. The lowering of this band in the complexes indicates the coordination of nitrogen atoms of azomethine

groups to the thallium^{4,5}. The far-IR spectra exhibited bands at $600-250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ν_{Tl-C} ⁶.

It was observed that the binding energy of Tl4f in the starting material $PhTlCl_2$ or Ph_2TlCl was higher than their prepared molecular adducts. This observation concludes that the electron density on Tl metal ion has been increased by coordination of Schiff base ligands with thallium metal ion (Figs. 1 and 2)¹⁰. It was observed that O1s binding energy in $PhTlCl.SB$ and $Ph_2Tl.SB$ (where SB = Schiff base 1 to 12) molecular adducts were higher than O1s binding energy

Fig. 1. Tl4f binding energy (eV) in Ph_2TlCl and their molecular adducts $Ph_2Tl.SB$ (SB = Schiff base SB₁ to SB₁₂).

Fig. 2 Tl4f binding energy (eV) in PhTlCl₂ and their molecular adducts PhTlCl₂.SB (SB = Schiff base SB₁₃ to SB₂₀)

of their Schiff base ligands (Fig. 3). This observation concludes that oxygen atom of Schiff base ligand is also bonded with thallium metal ion. The PhTlCl₂.SB and Ph₂TlCl.SB (where SB = 12 to 20) molecular adducts have not shown O1s photoelectron peak as it is evident from

Fig. 3 O1s binding energy in PhTlCl SB and Ph₂Tl SB (SB = Schiff base SB₁ to SB₃)

elemental analysis. The N1s photoelectron peak in all these molecular adducts PhTlCl.SB and Ph₂Tl.SB (where SB = 1 to 12), PhTlCl₂.SB and Ph₂TlCl.SB (where SB = 12 to 20) have shown much higher binding energy than N1s binding energy of their Schiff base ligands (Fig. 4). These observations suggest that nitrogen atom of Schiff base ligand is coordinated to central metal ion¹⁰. The Tl3s photoelectron peak of all the prepared molecular adducts have shown single symmetrical peak without any splitting in photoelectron peak. This observation in Tl3s photoelectron peaks confirms the diamagnetic nature of the molecular adducts¹⁰.

Fig. 4 N1s binding energy (eV) in PhTlCl₂.SB, Ph₂TlCl SB (SB = Schiff base SB₁₃ to SB₁₅)

On the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity results, showing the complexes to be non-ionic and IR and X-ray photoelectron (XPS) identifying the site of coordination, it is possible to conclude that the PhTlCl.SB and Ph₂Tl.SB (where SB = 1 to 12) are tetrahedral (sp^3 hybridization) but PhTlCl₂.SB and Ph₂TlCl.SB (where SB = 13 to 20) are trigonal bipyramidal (sp^3d hybridization).

Experimental

PhTlCl₂^{7,8} and Ph₂TlCl⁹ were synthesized and characterized by reported methods.

Schiff base ligands (SB₁ to SB₁₂): 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-5 methylpropiophenone or 2-hydroxy-5-methylbutyrophenone or salicylaldehyde (1 mmol) in 50 ml of methanol was mixed with aniline or *p*-toluidine or *p*-anisidine (1 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h. TLC suggested complete conversion of the above ketone or aldehyde to Schiff base. The solid products

were stored *in vacuo* and characterized by C, H and N analyses.

Schiff base ligands (SB₁₃ to SB₂₀) : A mixture of 2-acetylpyrrole/2-pyrrolicarboxylaldehyde/2-pyridylcarboxylaldehyde/2-naphthylaldehyde (2 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) and *o*-phenylenediamine/ethylenediamine (1 mmol) was refluxed for ~3 h. TLC suggested complete conversion of ketone or aldehyde to Schiff base. The solid product obtained after rotary evaporation was air-dried and characterized by C, H and N analyses. The following eight such Schiff base ligands were prepared (SB₁₃-SB₂₀) :

SB₁₃ = bis(2-acetylpyrrole)ethylenediamine

SB₁₄ = bis(2-acetylpyrrole)ethylenediamine

SB₁₅ = bis(2-pyrrolicarboxylaldehyde)phenylenediamine

SB₁₆ = bis(2-pyrrolicarboxylaldehyde)ethylenediamine

SB₁₇ = bis(2-pyridylcarboxylaldehyde)phenylenediamine

SB₁₈ = bis(2-pyridylcarboxylaldehyde)ethylenediamine

SB₁₉ = bis(2-naphthylaldehyde)phenylenediamine

SB₂₀ = bis(2-naphthylaldehyde)ethylenediamine

PhTlCl₂SB and Ph₂TlClSB complexes : A mixture of PhTlCl₂ or Ph₂TlCl (1 mmol) in dry CHCl₃ and the Schiff base ligand (1 mmol) was refluxed (~3 h). The solid product obtained after rotary evaporation was purified by pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°), air-dried and kept in desiccator.

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The microanalyses of the complexes were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Conductance was measured in acetone at room temperature using a Digisum electronics conduc-

tivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer.

The X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3 MK II electron spectrometer. The Mg K_α X-ray line (1253.6 eV) was used for photoexcitation. The Cu2p_{3/2} (BE = 932.8 ± 0.2) and Au4f_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 ± 0.1) lines were used to calibrate the instrument and Ag3d_{5/2} (BE = 368.2) was used for cross-checking¹⁰. All the spectra was recorded using the same spectrometer parameters of 50 eV pass-energy and 4 mm slit-width. The reduced full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) at Au4f_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 eV) level under these conditions was 1.2 eV.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, for facilities.

References

1. A. G. Lee, "The Chemistry of Thallium", Elsevier, New York, 1971.
2. G. K. Gaur, Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1998.
3. W. J. Greary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
4. T. N. Srivastava and M. A. Siddiqui, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 785.
5. T. N. Srivastava, A. K. S. Chauhan and G. K. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 22, 712.
6. M. Tanka, H. Kurosawa and R. Okawara, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1967, 3, 565.
7. F. Challenger and B. Parker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1462.
8. F. R. Bean and J. R. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4415.
9. D. Goddard and A. E. Goddard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 256.
10. S. Srivastava, *Applied Spectrosc. Rev.*, 1986, 22, 401.